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	French:	Outil de test de chargement et de performance intégré pour serveurs d'application	[2011/01]
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	Search	[X] US2005039171 (AVAKIAN ARRA E et al.) * abstract * * paragraph [0045] - paragraph [0072] * * paragraph [0131] - paragraph [0144] * * paragraph [0150] - paragraph [0183] *
		[I] US2009138858 (LIVSHITS BENJAMIN et al.) * abstract * * paragraph [0028] - paragraph [0066] * * paragraph [0072] - paragraph [0074] *
Documents cited:		[I] US2007083649 (ZUZGA BRIAN et al.) * abstract * * paragraph [0007] - paragraph [0022] * * paragraph [0055] - paragraph [0069] * * paragraph [0075] - paragraph [0083] * * paragraph [0085] - paragraph [0092] * * paragraph [0110] - paragraph [0120] * * paragraph [0127] - paragraph [0144] *
		[I] US2008306711 (BANSAL JYOTI et al.) * abstract * * paragraph [0028] - paragraph [0071] *

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